

Karana abscondita sp. n. from China (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae, Dypterygiini)

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Abstract. A new species, *Karana abscondita* sp. n. is described from China, Sichuan. The main external and genitalia diagnostic features of the new species and of its closest relative *Karana prima* Hreblay & Ronkay, 1998 is characterised and discussed and illustrated with four colour figures, while the genitalia are presented with five monochromatic figures.

Keywords. *Karana*, new species, description, taxonomy.

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Introduction

The genus *Karana* Moore, 1882 (Noctuidae, Dypterygiini) is represented with 12 species and 4 subspecies, distributed from the Far East and Japan toward SE Asia and one species is also known from New Guinea. *Karana* is the most diverse in SE China, Himalaya and Thailand.

The author of this article studied *Karana* material in his own collection and managed to find a short series of a new species to science, collected by S. Murzin in a remote region of China, Sichuan. Although the species *K. prima* is very similar to the new species at first glance, a closer look clearly shows that there are striking differences in the wing pattern elements of the forewings, the colouration and wing pattern of the hindwings and especially in the male and female genitalia structure.

Abbreviations for personal and institutional collections used herein are as follows: BMNH = collection in the British Museum Natural History, London, Great Britain; MH in HNHM = collection of Márton Hreblay in Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest, Hungary; PGM = collection of Péter Gyulai (Miskolc, Hungary). Other abbreviations used: BM Noct N = genitalia slide number in the BMNH; GYP = genitalia slide prepared by Péter Gyulai; HM = genitalia slide prepared by Márton Hreblay; m = male; f = female; HT = holotype; PT = paratype.

Description of new species.

***Karana abscondita* sp. n.** (Figs 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8)

Holotype. male (Fig. 1), China, Sichuan prov., Lingshan Mts., 2600 m, 20 km W of Mianning, 17–18. VIII. 2007, leg. S. Murzin, GYP 5065 (coll. PGM).

Paratypes. 6 males, 1 female, with the same data, GYP 4611m, 5360f (coll. PGM).

Diagnosis. Male specimens of *Karana abscondita* sp. n. (Figs 1, 3) can be distinguished from the males of the most similar and closest relative *Karana prima* Hreblay & Ronkay, 1998 (Fig. 2) by the broader basal and antemedial lines in the forewings (although the new species is smaller) and the much darker, brown (and not whitish-light greyish) hindwings, having a

much broader and darker, diffuse brown medial stripe and marginal area. Additionally, all of the wings have a slight red-brown suffusion in the new species, which is lacking in *K. prima*. The hindwings of the female of *K. abscondita* sp. n. are basally white then whitish, and broadly diffuse, and darker brown toward the marginal area; while they are almost unicolourous dark grey brown in *K. prima* (written in the original description by Hreblay & Ronkay, 1998; photo was not available from London). Additionally, the new species is smaller (29–33 mm) than *K. prima* (36–42 mm).

In the male genitalia capsule, *K. abscondita* sp. n. (Figs 5, 6) differs from that of *K. prima* (Fig. 7) by the somewhat shorter, dorsally less inward curved, terminally broader valvae on the ventral side, more asymmetric and differently shaped harpe (particularly in the left side). In the distal end of the vesica of the new species, the diverticulum is broader, and not scobinate, the bar-like cornutus sitting on its posterior-lateral side is weaker but somewhat longer than in *K. prima*. However, the most remarkable difference is that in the new species the distal lateral part of the vesica bears a large lenticular scobinate plate, whilst in *K. prima* the equivalent feature is a lateral, long bar.

In the female genitalia, *K. abscondita* sp. n. (Fig. 8) has remarkable shorter antrum, significantly longer, curved ductus bursae and larger, more prominent appendix bursae, than in *K. prima* (Fig. 9).

Description. (Figs 1, 3, 4). Wingspan 29–33 mm. Antennae filiform in both sexes. Vestiture of the head and thorax blackish and dark brownish, with slight whitish irroration; that of the abdomen lighter. Forewing ground colour metallic shining blackish - dark brownish, with slight dark red-brownish suffusion. Most parts of the wing pattern obscure; the almost straight basal and antemedial lines, the large reniform stigmata, the end of the basal streak and a spot inside the black claviform stigmata are clearly white defined, conspicuous. Cilia brownish. Hindwing whitish brown suffused in the basal part, then darker and darker brownish, with darker cellular spot and diffuse medial line; the veins with a darker brown tinge. Cilia whitish with fine, pale brown sections. The underside of forewings dark brownish, un-patterned; the hindwings lighter brownish, whitish in the basal field, with the obscure ghost of the wing pattern on the upper side. The forewings of the female lack the dark reddish suffusion, while the hindwings have a large white field in the basal- and medial part.

Male genitalia (Figs 5, 6). The uncus thin, pointed. Penicular lobes are armed with a conspicuous, extended field of several, dark brownish, flattened, cornutus-like scales dorsally. Vinculum is broadly V-shaped. Fultura inferior a large, rounded plate. The valvae elongate, with a moderate medial extension on both sides, then symmetrically narrowing toward the cucullus. The cucullus broad, dorsally tapering, apically rounded; corona broadly armed with a field of fine, long cornuti, and with a broad setose field outside. The aedeagus curved, cylindrical, carina extended onto the subbasal vesica with a sclerotized line, ended in a small scobinate field. The vesica broad, semiglobular and recurved dorsad, possessing in the distal part a large diverticulum with a bar-like, almost evenly thin, long, apically with a tiny, dentate cornutus, sitting on its posterior-lateral side. Additionally, in the inner curve of the distal lateral part of the vesica, bears a large lenticular scobinate plate.

Female genitalia (Fig. 8). *K. abscondita* **sp. n.** has short, broad papillae anales, broadly funnel-like, strongly sclerotized antrum, long, curved ductus bursae, saccular corpus bursae with large, conical, prominent appendix bursae.

Etymology. The Latin name of the new species means “hidden”, because among the many externally very similar species it was not recognized for a long time.

Distribution. The new species is known only from the Lingshan Mts., Sichuan, China.

Figures 1–4. *Karana* spp. adults. **1.** *K. abscondita* **sp. n.**, HT, m, China, Sichuan, Lingshan, leg. S. Murzin, GYP 5065 (PGM); **2.** *K. prima* Hreblay & Ronkay, 1998, HT, m, China, Siao-Lou, Chasseurs Indigènes, leg. P. Dejean, 1903, HM 6681 (BM Noct N 15531) (BMNH) (photo by M. Hreblay); **3.** *K. abscondita* **sp. n.**, PT, m, China, Sichuan, Lingshan, leg. S. Murzin (PGM), **4.** *K. abscondita* **sp. n.**, PT, f, China, Sichuan, Lingshan, leg. S. Murzin, GYP 5360 (PGM).

Figures 5–7. *Karana* spp. male genitalia. **5.** *K. abscondita* sp. n., HT, China, Sichuan, Lingshan, GYP 5065 (PGM); **6.** *K. abscondita* sp. n., PT, China, Sichuan, Lingshan, GYP 4611 (PGM); **7.** *K. prima* Hreblay & Ronkay, 1998, HT, m, China, Siao-Lou, Chasseurs Indigènes, leg. P. Dejean, 1903, HM 6681 (BM Noct N 15531) (BMNH) (after Hreblay & Ronkay, 1998).

Figures 8–9. *Karana* spp. female genitalia. **8.** *K. abscondita* sp. n., PT, f, China, Sichuan, Lingshan, GYP 5360 (PGM); **9.** *K. prima* Hreblay & Ronkay, 1998, PT, f, China, Siao-Lou, Chasseurs Indigènes, leg. P. Dejean, 1903, HM 6682 (BM Noct N 15532) (after Hreblay & Ronkay, 1998).

Figure 10. Type locality (black circle) of *Karana abscondita* sp. n.: China, Sichuan prov., Lingshan Mts., 2600 m, 20 km W of Mianning (© Map by I. Fazekas, 2025)

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